

TRANSFORMATIVE IMPACT OF HEALTH LITERACY AND HEALTHY LIVING ON PREGNANT GIRLS AND WOMEN IN URBAN SLUMS

By

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Abstract

Girls and women living in urban slums face far greater challenges than their counterparts in more stable environments. Limited access to quality education, poor parental support, neglect, and restrictive cultural norms expose them to heightened risks of exploitation, including involvement in sex-work and early unintended pregnancies; conditions that perpetuate cycles of vulnerability and poverty. As a result, pregnant girls and women in this marginalized environment encounter multiple health, social, and economic difficulties that severely compromise maternal and child health outcomes. High rates of maternal and infant morbidity and mortality in these areas are driven by poor access to quality healthcare, inadequate prenatal services, poor nutrition, and low levels of health literacy.

This paper examines the pivotal role of health literacy and healthy living as transformative tools for empowering vulnerable pregnant girls and women in urban slums. It contends that enhancing knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors around reproductive health, personal hygiene, nutrition, and healthcare access can serve as a sustainable strategy for breaking cycles of poor health and social inequality. The study also emphasizes the importance of culturally-sensitive, community-based interventions that equip marginalized women and girls with the information, skills, and resources needed to make informed decisions about their health and well-being.

Finally, the study recommends for integrated, inclusive approaches that prioritize education, healthcare access, and sustained community support as essential pathways to achieving equity in maternal health and promoting healthier, more resilient slum communities.

Keywords: health literacy, healthy living, outcomes, pregnant girls and women, urban slums

Introduction

The existence of slum is a global phenomenon. According to the United Nations Program on Human Settlements (UN-HABITAT), a slum is defined as “a contagious settlement where the inhabitants are characterized as having inadequate housing and basic services. Globally, it was highlighted that there was an increase in the number of people living in slum; the number was reported to be 1 billion with an expected increase of another 1 billion by the year 2030. According to the UN-Habitat report of 2019, an expected 70% increase in the number of people residing in slums will occur by 2050. Shittu et al (2018) noted that most of these slum dwellers are found in Africa, where informal settlements are highly concentrated. Varying degree of names has been attributed to slum across the globe, as its definition is qualitative. In the present time, the synonyms used for slums are informal settlement, squatter, shanty town, ghetto, favelas, township, aashawa and few to mention (Asha, 2023).

Succintly, slum communities are characterized by substandard living conditions, including inadequate basic amenities- drinkable water, electricity, food, health, good hygiene, housing, education and good toilet facilities). Girls and women living in urban slums encounter challenges than their counterparts in more stable environments. Limited access to quality education, poor parental support, neglect, and restrictive cultural norms expose them to heightened risks of exploitation, including involvement in sex-work and early unintended pregnancies; conditions that perpetuate cycles of vulnerability and poverty. As a result, pregnant girls and women in this setting encounter health, social, and economic difficulties that severely compromise maternal and child health outcomes. Growing evidence asserts that high rates of maternal and infant morbidity and mortality in these areas are driven by poor access to quality healthcare, inadequate prenatal services, poor nutrition, and low levels of health literacy; poor health literacy in large proportions of the population of both developed and developing countries (Essam, Khafagy, and Alemam, 2022).

Unwanted pregnancies among Adolescent poses a serious public health challenge that has well-defined causes, associated health risks, and social and economic consequences for Adolescent their families, communities and society (Amodu et al.. 2022). Slum communities which are characterized by sub-standard living conditions, including inadequate housing, lack of basic services like water and sanitation and often limited access to education and healthcare.

Disadvantaged girls and women living in these communities are prone to these barriers. Longitudinal studies revealed that randomized controlled trials and interventions to improve health literacy in pregnant girls and women are so rare. Hence, the framework addresses stressors among vulnerable pregnant girls and women, concept of health literacy and healthy living, dimensions of health literacy, stakeholders in health literacy, role of health literacy and healthy living as improving outcomes, conclusion and recommendations.

Stressors encountered among Vulnerable Pregnant girls and women in Urban Slums

The term stress refers to the bodily reaction to a perceived challenge, demand or threat leading to physical, mental, and emotional strain. When stress is chronic it affects the body negatively and impairs health, wellbeing and daily job activities. The impact of stressors is mediated by coping and adaptive strategies, forms of resilience that buffer the adverse effect on health and wellbeing.

Pregnancy is one of the psychological stress encountered among women in larger population and responding to it differently differs from one person to the other. Women in marginalized settings and in low income group often experience disproportionate levels of stressors stemming from household responsibilities, gender inequalities, malnutrition, dietary inadequacy and violence (with intimate partner), the transition in social role associated with becoming a mother (Ahmed et al., 2017), inadequate knowledge of pregnancy periods cause a shift in stress especially among pregnant girls who dropped out of school. All these stressors have a major implication for public health, not only for the mother but also for the offspring who may be exposed to physiological signals of stress through the placenta (Bronson and Bale 2016).

The negative impact of stress on maternal and fetal health and nutrition during pregnancy can lead to birth outcome such as shorter gestational age, prolonged labour, abortion, still birth, low birth weight, congenital anomalies, maternal perinatal infection, preeclampsia and hemorrhage (Traylor, Johnson, Kimmel, and Manuck, 2020). Perinatal complications and prolonged labour were associated with antenatal common mental disorders among Ethiopian women.

Children born to stress mothers have increased risk of morbidity, cognitive disability and some may have elevated risk of mental and behavioural problems during childhood such as anxiety, depression and attention deficit disorder. These instances contributed to the persistent burden of growth and development among children in urban slums. Finally, as a result of high risk job of

girls in slum areas such as prostitution, they have high risk of non-communicable diseases (NCDs). Thus stress is capable of contributing to high rate of mortality and other underlying health conditions among vulnerable pregnant girls and women in urban slums.

To ameliorate this it is pertinent to understand the pivotal role of health literacy, healthy living as interventions to improve outcomes among vulnerable pregnant girls and women in urban slums

Concept of Health Literacy

Global Definition of Health Literacy (HL)

Over the years attention has been given to the concept of health literacy due to its significant benefits to individuals and public health and the sustainability of goal three of the development goals (Sorensen et al., 2012). According to world health organisation (WHO), HL can be define as the cognitive and social skills that determine the motivation and ability of individuals to gain access, understand and use information in ways that promote and maintain good health (Essam, et al. 2022). Other researchers have explained their view point on the concept. According to Schulz and Nakamoto 2012 highlighted knowledge as the core tenet in the concept of HL. Their identification of HL is seen as set of basic literacy, declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge and judgement skills. In similar vein Paakkari and Paakkari, 2012 argued that self-awareness and citizenship also form a part of health literacy as they represent one's ability to access oneself in an informed way and to take responsibility to improve health beyond personal perspective.

Apart from the above definitions, some researchers attempted to conceptualize HL from other views; for instance, Soellner, Lenartz, Rudinger 2017 proposed the addition of self-perception, proactive health approach to health, self-regulation and self-control into the concept of HL.

Health literacy plays a crucial role in addressing maternal mortality, particularly among vulnerable groups such as pregnant girls and women. It underscores the importance of empowering women to actively manage their own health and make informed use of available health services. A lack of health literacy is often linked to difficulties in understanding health information, limited awareness of diseases, and poor medication adherence. These challenges contribute to adverse health outcomes, underutilization of health services, higher healthcare costs, and widening health disparities (Sheridan, Halpern, & Viera, 2011).

An increasing body of research identifies health literacy as one of the most promising and cost-effective strategies for reducing maternal mortality risks among vulnerable girls and women in unstable populations. Recognizing its significance, developed countries such as United States, China, Australia, member states of the European Union, and Canada have integrated health literacy as a central priority in their health policies and programs (Pleasant & McKinney, 2011).

Pivotal Role of Health Literacy

Health literacy is considered important when the circumstance of mortality arises especially among vulnerable pregnant girls and women highlighting the need for women to take more responsibility in managing their own health with more effective use of health services. Inability of having understanding of health literacy is associated with difficulty in comprehension of health information, limited knowledge of diseases and lower medication adherence, which contribute to poor health, insufficient and ineffective use of health care, increasing costs and health disparities (Sheridan, Halpern and Viera 2011). Growing body of literature have suggested health literacy as one of the most cost-effective approaches to overcome mortality challenges among vulnerable pregnant girls and women. Inclusion of health literacy as a key priority in policies and practices has been embedded in some developed countries such as USA, China, Australia, European Union and Canada (Pleasant and Mckinney, 2011).

Dimensions of Health Literacy (HL)

Jordan, et al., 2010 proposed three dimensions of HL;

- Identifying a health issue
- Engaging in information exchange
- Acting on health information

Empirical studies on health literacy revealed that having low level of health literacy has negative consequences for one's health and for the uptake of health system services. It is also associated to poor adherence to medication, health outcomes and higher risk of hospitalisation (Berkman et al 2011). Results from Essam et al 2022 revealed a higher proportion of limited HL among women who do not frequently use the internet as a source of information. Not only the reading and writing of HL, using internet helps people to develop HL. This limited HL is common among women who either married or had their first child at young age. Reported cases of most

women in Afghanistan with limited inadequate HL do not know how to prevent unwanted pregnancy (Harsch et al., 2022). Health literacy statistics according to Moreira, 2018 indicated that;

- ❖ 47% of adult find reading about health information challenging
- ❖ 41% of adults cannot weigh up advantages and disadvantages when comparing medical treatments
- ❖ 37% would not know when to seek clarification from a second doctor
- ❖ 35% find it challenging to interpret information on food label
- ❖ 32% would not know how to seek health information on how to manage their mental health

Stakeholders involved in Health Literacy

Healthy Living

Healthy living involves a holistic approach that integrates physical, mental, and social well-being. It requires making conscious and sustained efforts to improve overall health while reducing the risk of chronic diseases among adult most especially vulnerable pregnant girls and women. Key components of healthy living include maintaining a well-balanced diet, engaging in regular physical activity, ensuring adequate sleep, and managing stress effectively.

In line with this research, a framework has been developed for both policy implementation and academic engagement. This model, **HER LIFE**, serves as intervention tool for enhancing health literacy and healthy living among pregnant girls and women; the role of women as bearer of life and as essential stakeholder in promoting family and community health cannot be undermined. Hence the framework is detailed as follows:

- **H** — *Health Empowerment*: Promoting women's ability to make informed health decisions.
- **E** — *Engagement in Care*: Encouraging active participation in health services and decision-making.
- **R** — *Resilience*: Strengthening mental, emotional, and social support systems for women.
- **L** — *Lifestyle Education*: Providing education on nutrition, hygiene, physical activity, and stress management.
- **I** — *Inclusive Services*: Ensuring equitable access to health services for girls and women across all communities.
- **F** — *Facilitated Access*: Delivering services through community outreach, mobile health units, and localized support systems.
- **E** — *Equitable Outcomes*: Striving for improved maternal and child health outcomes across social and economic groups.

Notably, there is a significant link between maternal health literacy and healthy pregnancy outcomes, as highlighted by Mojinyinola (2011). This underscores the importance of empowering women with knowledge and resources for better health management and positive maternal outcomes.

Conclusion

The paper examined health literacy and healthy living as intervention for improved outcomes among pregnant women in urban slums. Health literacy demonstrates the need of overcoming mortality challenges among pregnant girls and women in stable and unstable environments. The understanding of health literacy allows women to know information relating to their health and up-date on the process of their pregnancy journey. The role of health literacy as transformative tools cannot be over-emphasized. Across cultures, the risk in mortality among pregnant is on the rise particularly among girls and women in urban slums. All stakeholders must stress the need of breaking cycles of poor health and social inequality; promoting maternal health and healthy living among pregnant girls and women in these settings.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the study recommends that pregnant girls and women irrespective of their age should not be ashamed of what they don't know. The need to access information, have adequate knowledge and living healthy lifestyle can improve success in intervention for these marginalized women and girls in urban slums.

Health practitioners should find a way of making reading of health documents improved and more enjoyable during ante-natal programmes or any health visiting day. This can come in form of tools to support the reading ability of the marginalized in these settings.

Health care givers, health educators and government parastatals must develop a working policy implementation that can serve as an intervention tool for enhancing health literacy and healthy living for not only pregnant girls and women but for larger population.

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